

Epigenetics in plant organismic interactions

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Abstract

Plants are hubs of organismic interactions. They constantly engage in beneficial or competitive interactions with fungi, oomycetes, bacteria, insects, nematodes, and other plants. To adjust the molecular processes necessary for the establishment and maintenance of beneficial interactions and for the defense against pathogens and herbivores, plants have evolved intricate regulatory mechanisms. Besides the canonical plant immune system that acts as the primary defense, epigenetic mechanisms have started to emerge as another regulatory entity and as a target of pathogens trying to overcome the plant's defenses. In this review, we highlight recent advances in understanding the contribution of various epigenetic components and of epigenetic diversity to plant-organismic interactions.

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Introduction

Plants constantly face pressure from their biotic environment and have evolved multiple layers of defense. Thorns, spikes, and cuticular barriers are the most obvious physical hurdles that herbivores and pathogens need to overcome. Beyond those, they often face a highly complex and effective chemical arsenal of specialized (aka secondary) plant metabolites, which are

designed to deter animals, fungi, oomycetes, bacteria, or other plants [1]. Finally, at the molecular level, plants have developed a broad recognition repertoire to compensate for the lack of an adaptive immune system. Plant immunity mainly relies on the perception of pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) or of microbial effector proteins. PAMP-triggered immunity (PTI) involves diverse responses such as stomata closure, production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitric oxide, biosynthesis of antimicrobial compounds, and hormonal defense responses involving salicylic acid (SA), jasmonic acid (JA), and ethylene (ET) [2]. Some pathogens can suppress PTI through the production of effector proteins that translocate into the plant cell; in a second line of plant defense, such effectors are recognized by R (resistance) proteins, leading to effector-triggered immunity (ETI), which induces programmed cell death to prevent the intruder from spreading throughout the plant tissue [3]. The signaling cascades of PTI and ETI converge downstream in activating common immunity-related genes [4].

At the same time, plants need to engage in beneficial cross-kingdom interactions, for example, with fungi and bacteria, to ensure nutrient uptake and exchange [5]. As a result, diverse strategies evolved to distinguish friend from foe and to ensure survival and fitness in changing biotic environments [6]. The proper distinction from wanted and unwanted interactions requires a fine-tuned adjustment of the regulatory systems.

While the relevance of host genotype for biotic interactions has been known for a long time, recent studies have highlighted that the plant *epigenotype*—the epigenetic configuration of the host genome at one or several genomic loci—is also a part of the equation [7]. In turn, there is accumulating evidence that the plant epigenetic machinery is directly involved in plant defense responses [8] and in the establishment of memory to environmental stress (reviewed in Refs. [9,10]). Therefore, both the epigenetic configuration of the host and the effect of biotic interactions thereon play a role in such responses. The epigenetic makeup of plants (and of most eukaryotic organisms) consists of the totality of DNA methylation, histone modifications, and—depending on the definition—small RNAs (sRNAs). Alone or in combination, these epigenetic marks define local chromatin accessibility, which ultimately determines gene expression and

hence also potentially contributes to plant defense, establishment of symbiosis, and so on.

In this review, we revisit the recent literature on the role of epigenetics in the establishment and modulation of plant biotic interactions. Readers interested in the epigenetic contribution to antiviral defense are referred to two recent reviews on the topic [11,12]. Because the interaction systems studied so far have been very diverse, we decided to structure our review by the type of epigenetic modification rather than by organism. Towards the end, we will elaborate on what we think are future questions worth addressing in the field.

DNA methylation in interactions with pests

Among the epigenetic mechanisms that control gene expression in eukaryotes, the one studied most extensively is DNA methylation [13,14]. Two types of DNA methylation have been detected in plant genomes: rare N⁶-adenosine methylation [15] and 5-cytosine methylation. Here, we will use the term DNA methylation interchangeably with 5-cytosine methylation. In plants, DNA methylation occurs in the symmetric contexts CG and CHG and in the asymmetric context CHH (where H is any base but G). CG methylation is the type mainly found in protein-coding genes, while repetitive sequences and transposable elements are generally densely methylated in all contexts [16,17]. Symmetric CG and CHG DNA methylation are maintained by the DNA methyltransferase MET1 and the plant-specific methyltransferase CHROMOMETHYLASE 3, respectively; the latter functionally links DNA methylation and dimethylation of lysin 9 of histone H3 (H3K9me₂) [18,19]. *De novo* DNA methylation in all contexts is controlled by the RNA-directed DNA methylation (RdDM) pathway, involving DOMAINS REARRANGED DNA METHYLTRANSFERASE 2 (DRM2) [20]. Alternatively, CHH methylation is under the control of CMT2 in cross-talk with histone H3 methylation [21]. Removal of DNA methylation is carried out by DNA glycosylases of the DEMETER family via base excision [22]. In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, this family comprises *DME*, *REPRESSOR OF SILENCING 1* (*ROS1*), and *DEMETER-LIKE 1* and *2* [22]. DNA methylation can change dynamically in response to environmental cues, including abiotic and biotic stresses [23]. Moreover, because DNA methylation patterns can be copied from mother to daughter cells, it has been postulated as the carrier of heritable epigenetic information.

The role of DNA methylation in plant defense has been extensively characterized [24,25]. The general trend emerging from many studies is that DNA methylation negatively regulates plant defense; in other words, loss of DNA methylation correlates with enhanced resistance [26]. This is illustrated by the fact that several

Arabidopsis mutants depleted in DNA methylation, such as *met1-3* or the *drm1 drm2 cmt3* triple mutant, showed stronger resistance to the bacterial pathogen *Pseudomonas syringae* (*Pst*) and increased expression of defense-related genes compared with Columbia-0 (Col-0) wild-type plants [27,28]. This is in spite of these mutants having fundamentally different DNA methylation patterns: While *met1-3* has severely reduced global CG methylation, *drm1 drm2 cmt3* is depleted of CHG and—to a lesser extent—CHH methylation [29], suggesting that there might be a hub at which these two DNA methylation pathways converge in the context of plant defense. In line with this idea, *met1 nrpd2* double mutants (NRPD2 is a subunit of RNA polymerase IV, a central component of the RdDM pathway.) displayed enhanced resistance to *Pst* [30]. The same study showed that treatment of *Arabidopsis* with the bacterial flagellin-derived peptide FLG22 caused downregulation of key components of the RdDM pathway [30], resulting in decreased CHH methylation levels. Together, these data indicate that DNA demethylation—potentially in combination with the deposition of specific histone marks—might be a priming signal that predisposes defense-related genes to be rapidly expressed during an ensuing infection by the same or another pathogen. Following that rationale, methylation-deficient mutant plants would be “mimicking” this primed state and thus respond more rapidly and/or more efficiently when exposed to a pathogen. The same group recently showed that *ROS1* is necessary to prevent gene-silencing RdDM from spreading from proximal transposable elements (TEs) into the promoter of the defense-related gene *RECEPTOR-LIKE PROTEIN 43*; failure to do so resulted in masking of the binding site of PAMP-responsive WRKY transcription factors [31,32].

But the relationship might be more complicated than a strict promotion of defense by hypomethylation or demethylation. López Sanchez et al. observed antagonistic effects of *Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis* (*Hpa*; downy mildew) infection in hypermethylated and hypomethylated mutants of *A. thaliana*: On the one hand, hypomethylated *nrpe* mutants (impaired in RNA polymerase V and hence in RdDM) were more tolerant to *Hpa*, and on the other hand, the hypermethylated *ros1* mutant was more susceptible [26]. These antagonistic responses correlated with opposite expression patterns of SA-dependent genes, upregulated in *nrpe* vs. *ros1*. However, the effect was inverse for infections with the necrotrophic pathogen *Plectosphaerella cucumerina*, with *nrpe* being more susceptible and JA-induced genes downregulated compared with *ros1*. Whether JA-responsive genes are a direct target of DNA methylation or whether there is a simultaneous upregulation of SA-responsive genes, which act antagonistically to the JA response, requires further investigation.

One might argue that it might be difficult to draw causal relationships by studying epigenetic pathway mutants with pleiotropic phenotypes. Epigenetic recombinant inbred lines (epiRILs) were established more than a decade ago in the model plant *A. thaliana* by crossing wild-type Col-0 to either *met1* [33] or *ddm1* [34] (The latter is a loss-of-function mutant of the chromatin remodeler DECREASE IN DNA METHYLATION 1 with a similarly depleted global methylation as *met1*). Descendants of this cross are near-isogenic but show

individual mosaic DNA methylation patterns [35,36]. epiRILs responded differently to JA and SA and varied in susceptibility to *Pst* infection, suggesting an underlying epigenetic cause [37–39]. Compelling evidence came from a recent study by Furci *et al.*: by measuring infection outcome with the biotrophic oomycete (*Hpa*) on more than 100 epiRILs from the Col-0 x *ddm1* cross, the authors identified four epigenetic quantitative trait loci (epiQTLs) explaining more than 60% of the variance in susceptibility [40] (Figure 1a and b). Lines

Figure 1

Locus-specific DNA hypomethylation promotes resistance to pathogens. (a) Epigenetic recombinant lines (epiRILs) were derived from a cross of regularly methylated (blue hairpins) *Arabidopsis thaliana* Col-0 wild-type with a methylation-depleted (white hairpins) *ddm1* mutant. For better visibility, methylation is indicated for only one chromatid of each homologous chromosome. F1 plants were selfed to generate several hundred F2 lines (Johannes *et al.*, 2009). Only lines carrying the homozygous *DDM1* wild-type allele were maintained. These lines were propagated for several generations by single-seed descent, resulting in lines with mosaic epigenotypes. (b) In generation F9, resistance of 123 epiRILs to the oomycete *Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis* (*Hpa*) was determined, and leaves were divided into phenotypic groups based on the level of *Hpa* colonization. By statistically testing for associations between infection levels and the sequenced epigenotype of all lines, Furci *et al.* identified four hypomethylated epigenetic quantitative trait loci (epiQTLs) correlating with elevated resistance; the red box schematically indicates one such epiQTL. (c) Mapped epiQTLs regulate defense-related genes *in trans*. Here, three hypothetical ways of transregulation are shown: short interfering RNAs (siRNAs) might arise from the hypomethylated epiallele and transregulate heterochromatin formation by sequence complementarity. By yet unresolved mechanisms, long intergenic noncoding RNAs (lincRNAs) can similarly change the chromatin configuration *in trans*. Ultimately, interactions among distant chromosomal loci could be altered by the change in the epigenetic configuration of one of these loci. Colored boxes are used to indicate physical loci.

carrying a hypomethylated allele of these epiQTLs displayed a primed state of many defense-related genes, but few of these genes were contained in the actual mapping intervals, suggesting regulation *in trans* by still unresolved mechanisms (Figure 1C).

Associations between loss of DNA methylation and plant defense are not limited to *Arabidopsis*: Hypomethylated rice plants treated with the DNA demethylating agent 5-azadeoxycytidine showed enhanced resistance to the bacterial pathogen *Xanthomonas* [41]. Recently, it was shown that infection of diploid wheat *Aegilops tauschii* with the biotrophic pathogen *Blumeria graminis f. sp. tritici* (*Bgt*) reduces ARGONAUTE4a levels as well as 24-nt siRNAs and CHH methylation in stress response genes that are in close proximity to TEs [42].

DNA methylation is not only implicated in the interaction with fungi or bacteria; several studies have characterized its role in plant-nematode interactions (For a full review on the topic, see Ref. [43]). Identification of differentially methylated regions in soybean in response to infection by the soybean cyst nematode *Heterodera glycines* revealed mostly hypomethylation in the plant root [44,45]. A recent follow-up study showed that some of these methylation changes affected the expression of plant microRNA (miRNA) genes [46], of which at least one played a role in the plant's response to the nematode.

DNA methylation in beneficial interactions

Recent studies highlighted the role of DNA methylation in symbiotic and commensal interactions [47]. In the legume *Medicago truncatula*, the homolog of *Arabidopsis* *DEMETER*, *MtDME*, is expressed in the differentiation zone of forming nitrogen-fixing nodules that arise from the symbiosis between *M. truncatula* and a *Sinorhizobium* bacterium. Suppression of *MtDME* prevented the formation of nodules and led to transcriptional misregulation of several hundred nodulation-related genes, including many members of the nodule-specific cysteine-rich (*NCR*) gene family that are essential for nodule formation [48]. In line with this, the successive endopolyploidization that is a hallmark of nodule formation correlated with DNA methylation changes in about half of all *NCR* genes [49]; a directional correlation between hypermethylation/hypomethylation and transcriptional downregulation/upregulation was not detectable. Because this study used reduced-representation bisulfite sequencing, the full extent or directionality of the methylation changes might have remained unclear. However, a recent study in soybean elucidated the association between DNA methylation, gene expression, and alternative splicing in soybean nodule development and identified CHH hypermethylation and CHG hypomethylation as prime features of the nodule methylome [50].

Very little and partially contradicting information is available on the role of epigenetic mechanisms in mycorrhizal symbiosis. According to two reports, colonization of two *Geranium* species by arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi caused increased DNA methylation levels in the host [51,52]. In contrast, arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi colonization in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) led to a specific transcriptional activation of certain *Copia* retroelements, suggesting a loss of suppressive DNA methylation at these loci [53]. All these studies had limited power to resolve DNA methylation changes at the genomic level but might serve as a starting point for more detailed future analyses.

Beyond bilateral interactions, it is interesting to ask whether the epigenetic setup of the host influences or reacts to the more general state of plant-microbe associations. The advent of high-throughput sequencing has enabled the quantitative and qualitative assessment of the holobiont, the combination of the host and all of its associated microorganisms [54]. Even though, to date, there does not seem to be a systematic investigation of such associations, first studies in this area provide intriguing insights that 'methylation moulds microbiomes' [55]. First evidence came from near-isogenic *A. thaliana* plants that had been regenerated via somatic embryogenesis and that carried epialleles related to the regeneration process and the tissue of origin of the embryos [56]. Plants regenerated from root-derived somatic embryos showed significantly different association with bacteria, both with regard to natural communities in soil and after inoculation with synthetic communities [56]. Vélchez et al. were able to establish a more direct association [57]. Plants often shape the quantitative and qualitative composition of their microbiota by the release of specialized (also known as secondary) metabolites [58]. This study showed that the synthesis of myo-inositol production is under the antagonistic regulation of *ROS1* and RdDM and that active demethylation of biosynthesis genes is required for the establishment of beneficial *Bacillus megaterium* in the rhizosphere of *A. thaliana* [57].

Small RNAs in cross-kingdom interactions

In the context of the very complex defense system that plants have evolved to protect themselves, noncoding RNAs act as key players by reprogramming host gene expression in response to infection of a wide range of microbes and pathogens. Besides their role in antiviral defense, which is outside the scope of this review, noncoding RNAs of different types have been implicated in the response to pathogens.

sRNA Movement between hosts and interacting organisms can induce gene silencing through cross-kingdom trafficking. One of the most intriguing recent findings was that *A. thaliana* packages sRNAs into

exosome-like vesicles. These vesicles accumulate at sites of infection by the fungal pathogen *Botrytis cinerea*. After fusion with the fungal cells, the vesicles deliver their content, and the sRNAs inhibit infection-relevant genes to attenuate or even prevent the attack [●●59]. However, pathogens have learned to make use of similar strategies by hijacking the plant's sRNA machinery. In a mechanism coined cross-kingdom RNA interference, the oomycete *Hpa* releases sRNAs into the plant cell (*A. thaliana*) and uses plant ARGONAUTE1 to suppress plant immunity [●●60]. A complex sRNA-mediated interaction was described between *A. thaliana* and the hemibiotrophic oomycete pathogen *Phytophthora capsici* [●●61]. Infection prompted locus-specific production of sRNAs that suppressed pathogen genes and thereby infection; however, the oomycete counteracts this plant defense by interfering with siRNA biogenesis. Altogether, these studies suggest that sRNAs, long thought to be exclusive antiviral agents, also act against microorganisms and that cross-kingdom RNAi is an essential element in plant immunity. Mobile mRNAs and miRNAs have also been implicated in plant-plant interactions; for example, mobile mRNAs moving between both species were detected in *Arabidopsis* and tomato plants parasitized by the dodder species *Cuscuta pentagona* [62,63]. MiRNAs transferred from *Cuscuta campestris* to its host *A. thaliana* were shown to benefit the parasite [64]. In the aforementioned examples, no altering of the chromatin state in either host or pathogen has been described, by which they do not fulfill the criteria of epigenetic regulation *sensu stricto*. It should be noted, however, that a systematic analysis of cross-kingdom epigenetic effects is lacking to date. Finally, while there are examples for sRNAs acting across *eukaryotic* kingdoms, their role in interactions between plants and bacteria remains unclear.

Histone modifications as a regulatory entity and a target

The third major epigenetic component are post-translational modifications (PTMs) of histones. Histone acetyltransferases (HATs) and deacetylases (HDACs), methyltransferases, and demethylases add or remove PTMs at the N-terminal histone tails that protrude from the core histone octamer [65]. Depending on the exact position of the amino acid that is modified and the type of modification, histone PTMs result in relaxed or condensed chromatin conformations, with the respective consequences for transcriptional activity. Histone acetylation favors an open chromatin configuration and therefore is associated with active transcription, while histone methylation can have an active or repressive effect on transcription depending on the residues that are modified [66]. Because of the dynamic machinery of writers and erasers that set and remove such PTMs, histone modifications can change very rapidly, inducing global transcriptional changes (Table 1) or impacting

transcription at a given genomic locus in response to an external signal such as an abiotic or biotic stress [10,67].

In the context of biotic stress, both HATs and HDACs have been involved in plant defense response. For example, the elongator complex subunits ELONGATOR PROTEIN2 (ELP2) and ELP3, both of which have acetyltransferase activity, have been involved in the basal defense response and in ETI. Mutation in ELP3 caused higher susceptibility to *P. syringae* *pv.* *maculicola* in *Arabidopsis* and a delay of defense gene induction after SA treatment or pathogen infection [68]. Similarly, an ELP2 subunit is required for rapid defense gene induction upon infection with bacterial or fungal pathogens [69,70]. *Arabidopsis elp2* mutants showed increased susceptibility to the necrotrophic fungi *B. cinerea* and failed to induce JA/ET defense pathway marker genes such as *PDF1.2*, *WRKY33*, and *ORA59* [70]. GCN5, another *Arabidopsis* HAT, regulated SA-mediated defense genes by acetylating H3K14 at their 5' and 3' ends [71]. Several studies have explored the role of HDACs in plant defense. Generally, HDACs have been described as negative regulators of SA-mediated defense response because most of the plant HDAC mutants studied so far showed increased resistance to diverse pathogen infections [27,72]. For instance, *Arabidopsis* mutants *hda19* and *hda6* are more resistant to *Pst* and show increased expression of SA-related defense genes *PR1* and *PR2* [73,74]. Similarly, mutants for the SRT2 deacetylase showed resistance to *Pst* infection and increased *PR1* expression [75]. In rice, silencing of the HDT 701 also caused elevated transcription of defense-related genes and a resistant phenotype to both *Magnaporthe oryzae* and *Xanthomonas oryzae* *pv.* *oryzae* pathogens [76]. *Arabidopsis* HDA9 negatively regulates plant defense via the regulation of nucleotide-binding leucine-rich repeat (*NLR*) gene expression. Double mutants of HDA9 and its interaction partner HOS15 (*hda9 hos15*) showed enhanced resistance to *Pst* and increased expression of the *NLR* gene *SCN1* under infection conditions [77]. In line with the role of HDACs as negative regulators of SA-mediated defense response, nitric oxide-mediated inhibition of HDACs increased acetylation in many genes involved in plant defense, including several SA defense genes [78]. Recently, another study uncovered a function of histone H2B in regulating bacterial defense when showing that H2B formed a regulatory module with the MAP kinase MPK3 that induced global genome acetylation changes during plant defense signaling [●79]. This study provided a mechanistic model for protein kinase signaling and its direct impact on chromatin landscape upon pathogen signaling. Contrary to the described resistance phenotypes of HDAC mutants, *h2b* mutants presented increased susceptibility to *Pst* [79]. In a very different scenario, HDACs become the target of the organismic interaction: Benzoxazinoids, plant-derived secondary metabolites that are produced in many grass species, can

Table 1

Post-translational histone modifications in plant-organismic interactions.

Chemical modification	Histone modification	Observations	Ref
Acetylation	H3K9ac and H3K14ac	Histone acetyltransferase GCN5 regulates H3K14ac levels at stress-related genes.	[71]
	H3K9ac	HDA9-HOS15 interaction regulates nucleotide-binding leucine-rich repeat or Nod-like receptor (<i>NLR</i>) gene expression via H3K9ac deposition during defense response. Double mutants <i>hda9 hos15</i> show enhanced resistance to <i>Pst</i> .	[77]
	H3K9ac and H3K14ac	Nitric oxide (NO)-mediated HDAC inhibition regulates expression of defense-related genes.	[78]
	pan-H3ac	Allelopathic benzoxazinoid-derived compound 2-amino-3H-phenoxazin-3-one (APO) inhibits HDAC activity, causing global increase of histone H3 acetylation and altered gene expression.	[•80]
	H3K9ac	Phytoplasma infection of <i>Paulownia fortune</i> alters transcriptional regulation.	[92]
	H4K12ac	Differential acetylation affects transcription of stress-responsive genes including resistant (R) proteins and stress-related transcription factors in <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> infected with rust (<i>Uromyces appendiculatus</i>).	[93]
	H3K9ac	Rice roots infected with nematode <i>Meloidogyne graminicola</i> show increased levels of H3K9ac at genes associated with defense response.	[94]
Methylation	H3K4me1/2/3 and H3K36me1/2/3	Histone methyl transferases SDG8 and SDG25 regulate global defense gene expression affecting H3K4 and H3K36 methylation. Single and double mutants show increased susceptibility to both <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> and <i>Pst</i> .	[85,86]
	H3K4me2/3	Rice histone lysine demethylase Jumonji704 (JMJ704) controls defense response to bacterial blight disease. JMJ704 suppresses transcription of defense negative regulators genes such as <i>NRR</i> , <i>OsWRKY62</i> , and <i>Os11N3</i> by reducing levels of the activating marks H3K4me2/3.	[82]
	H3K4me3 and H3K36me3	Altered transcriptional regulation of genes involved in metabolic pathways, biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, phenylpropanoid biosynthesis, plant-pathogen interaction, and plant hormone signal transduction during phytoplasma infection in <i>Paulownia fortune</i> .	[92]
	H3K4me2	Differential methylation affects transcription of stress-responsive genes including resistant (R) proteins, detoxifying enzymes, and genes involved in ion flux and cell death in <i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> infected with rust (<i>Uromyces appendiculatus</i>).	[93]
	H3K27me3	Loss of the polycomb repressive complex protein LHP1 induces reduction in H3K27me3 levels at jasmonic acid (JA) and abscisic acid (ABA)-induced TFs <i>ANAC019</i> and <i>ANAC055</i> as well as some of their targets. <i>Lhp1</i> mutants show increased aphid resistance, ABA sensitivity, and increased susceptibility to <i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> .	[95]
	H3K9me2/3	Dynamic histone regulation in root-knot nematode (<i>M. graminicola</i>) infection in rice. H3K27me3 is strongly enriched while H3K9me2 is generally depleted in galls formed in root upon infection. Differential histone peaks are associated with plant defense genes. Plants overexpressing two histone lysine methyltransferases (<i>OsSDG729</i> , <i>OsSDG740</i>) show contrasting susceptibility to <i>M. graminicola</i> .	[94]

inhibit the growth of neighboring species. The benzoxazinoid-derived compound 2-amino-3H-phenoxazin-3-one inhibited not only root growth of *A. thaliana* but also HDAC activity *in vitro* and caused global increase of histone H3 acetylation and altered gene expression [•80].

Histone methylation plays an ambiguous role in plant biotic interactions. Owing to the dynamic role of methylation in regulating transcription, both histone methyltransferases and demethylases have been proposed as positive or negative regulators of plant defense. The *Arabidopsis* demethylases JUMONJI 27 (*AtJMJ27*),

AtJMJ14, and INCREASE IN BONSAI METHYLATION 1, as well as the rice demethylase *OsJMJ704*, are positive regulators of defense. *AtJM27* and *OsJMJ704* suppress the transcription of master negative defense regulators: *AtJMJ27* represses *WRKY25* by removing H3K9me1/2, and *OsJMJ704* represses *OsWRKY66*, *OsNRR*, and *Os11N3* via H3K4me2/3 demethylation [81–84], while *AtJMJ14* and INCREASE IN BONSAI METHYLATION 1 are required for the expression of several defense genes involved in local and systemic defense [83,84]. The methyltransferases *SDG8* and *SDG25* have been implicated in PTI, ETI, and systemic acquired resistance against bacterial and fungal

pathogens. *sdg8* and *sdg25* single as well as *sdg8 sdg25* double mutants displayed increased susceptibility to both *B. cinerea* and *Pst* [85,86]. This susceptible phenotype was attributed to an altered global histone methylation profile at the carotenoid *CCR2* and *CER3* loci, involved in carotenoid and cuticular wax biosynthesis, respectively [85]. Interestingly, H2B ubiquitination was reduced at *CCR2*, *CER3*, and H2B-monoubiquitinated resistance gene *SNCI* in *sdg* mutants, indicating cross-talk between the histone methylation and ubiquitination [85]. Mutations in the methyltransferase gene *ATXR7* show reduced H3K4 methylation in *SNCI* and compromised resistance to *Hpa* [87]. Another study highlighted the importance of the TE-mediated modulation of H3K9me2 levels at the *A. thaliana* disease resistance gene *RPP7*. The *COPIA-R7* retrotransposon inserted within this gene recruits the histone mark H3K9me2 to this locus, affecting the choice between two alternative *RPP7* polyadenylation sites in the pre-mRNA and thereby influencing the critical balance between two distinct transcript isoforms [88].

Several recent studies investigated the role of chromatin remodeling in plant defense. The *Arabidopsis* SWI/SNF class chromatin remodeling ATPase SPLAYED (SYD) is a positive regulator of defense against necrotrophs. Walley *et al.* showed that SYD regulates the JA/ET response during *B. cinerea* infection and is crucial for the defense response, while it was not required in defense against *Pst* [89]. In *A. thaliana*, loss-of-function mutations in the PHOTOPERIOD-INDEPENDENT EARLY FLOWERING1 and SWR1 COMPLEX 6 subunits of the chromatin remodeling complex SWR1c compromised basal resistance and ETI, while subunit ACTIN-RELATED PROTEIN6 loss of function enhanced it [90]. Another study showed the role of MICROCHORDIA (MORC) proteins in regulating chromatin accessibility during plant-pathogen interaction: *A. thaliana morc1/2* mutants infected with *Pst* showed an enriched proportion of differential DNase hypersensitive sites at TEs, suggesting that MORCs modulate plant immune responses by binding to TEs, influencing both their expression and that of proximal genes following pathogen infection [91].

Conclusion

Besides host genotype (G), environment (E), and the interaction of both (G×E), host epigenotype is emerging as another component to be taken into consideration when investigating the relationship between plants and their biotic interactors. The examples provided here indicate that epigenetic regulation contributes to the outcome of plant defense, symbiosis, and parasitism. Future studies will be necessary to understand the molecular dependencies of the different layers of regulation and the impact of naturally occurring plant

epigenetic variation on biotic interactions. Moreover, most studies to date have focused on the epigenetic configuration of the host, while there are limited data on epigenetic mechanisms or variation in the interactors and how these might influence infection outcome. For example, in a rare investigation of epigenetic polymorphisms on the pathogen side, Wang *et al.* showed that epiallelic H3K27me3 caused silencing of the *Phytophthora sojae* avirulence effector gene Avr1b and allowed evasion of the host immune recognition [96]. Another major current limitation is that study systems have not been standardized in the field and often make it difficult to compare studies, either because different biotic interactors were chosen or because the general setup was different. Both these hurdles can be overcome by future collaborative efforts between the fields of microbiology, plant immunity, and epigenetics.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

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